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Strengthening the Marine Defense Strategy of Lanal Banten Area through Empowerment of the Traffic Separation Scheme in the Sunda Strait

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Abstract

Indonesia as an archipelagic country is gifted by God with a geographical location between two continents and also two oceans, making Indonesia's position very strategic. In accordance with UNCLOS 1982, as an archipelagic country, Indonesia has an obligation to provide a shipping route called ALKI (Indonesian Archipelago Sea Channel). ALKI 1 stretches from the Malacca Strait to the Sunda Strait. The Sunda Strait as one of the busy shipping lanes is vulnerable to various forms of threats. To ensure the safety of shipping in the Sunda Strait, the TSS of the Sunda Strait is designated as a shipping lane separating channel. With the determination of the TSS of the Sunda Strait, shipping using the Sunda Strait will be increasingly crowded, this will pose an even greater threat. The purpose of this study was to analyze the strengthening of the marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait carried out by Lanal Banten by utilizing the TSS of the Sunda Strait. The method used in this research is descriptive qualitative research using the theory of policy implementation from Van Meter Van Horn and strategy theory from Lykke. The results of the study indicate that the lack of facilities and infrastructure and the absence of a special operation carried out by the Indonesian Navy to secure the Sunda Strait, so that the implementation of strengthening the marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait has not been optimal. There needs to be support for facilities and infrastructure as well as support for special operations in the Sunda Strait to strengthen the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait and the participation of the people around the Sunda Strait.

Keywords: ALKI, Marine Defense Strategy, TSS OF Sunda Strait

Introduction

Indonesia as an archipelagic country is gifted by God with a geographical location between two continents and also two oceans, making Indonesia's position very strategic. Indonesian waters are passed by ships that will pass both for trade and for other activities. We can see the world's interest in Indonesian waters where Japan as an industrial country has eighty percent of raw materials as well as industrial products are shipped through Indonesian waters, coal and iron ore originating from Australia are exported to their destination countries through Indonesian waters, eastern countries. middle as an oil exporter using tankers through Indonesian waters as well, in military interests, warships from China, the United States, Russia, India, and other countries need Indonesian waters to carry out cross navigation. At the International Law of the Sea Convention (LOSC) convention or what we know as the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) in 1982, which we know as the UN convention that discusses International sea law in 1982, Indonesia was designated as an archipelago. . In accordance with the agreement, Indonesia has sovereignty in the sea which is recognized by the international community which must pay attention to the rights owned by other countries in terms of the right of peaceful passage so that Indonesia must provide an international shipping channel which we call ALKI (Indonesian Archipelago Sea Channel) as a sea shipping channel can be used. Indonesia is designated as an archipelagic country, in accordance with UNCLOS 1982 which is explained in article 46 to article 53. In this article, Indonesia can determine shipping lanes that can be used by foreign ships in conducting cross-peaceful voyages. On the Indonesian shipping route, there are 4 choke points, one of which is the Sunda Strait (Marsetio, 2014). With a strategic geographical position the Sunda Strait is a busy strait and is passed by many ships to sail, every year there are 70,000 ships crossing the Sunda Strait (Kemenhub, 2017). As one of the straits with busy traffic and also the entry point for international shipping that will use ALKI 1, the Sunda Strait becomes the main trade route between the Australian continent and the Asian continent. With the busy number of ships passing through the Sunda Strait, there are many threats and disturbances. Not only the threat of navigation but also other threats that can disrupt the survival of the nation, one of which is drug smuggling. In 2016, drug trafficking in the form of 54 kg of methamphetamine and 40,894 ecstasy pills was successfully thwarted by the Police at the port (Indonesia, 2017). In July 2017, the National Police arrested 1 tonne of methamphetamine smugglers, using a route starting from the South China Sea to Johor, then along the western coast to enter the Sunda Strait (Badriyanto, 2017). The Sunda Strait also became an arena for the British ability to showcase the "Show of Force" on August 24, 1964 using the HMS Victorious with two distroyer ships escorting from Singapore to Australia using the Sunda Strait route without permission (Ajinugroha, 2020) to Indonesia although in the end Indonesia was able to thwart it. Judging from the situation above, the Sunda Strait is an opportunity and also a challenge that must be answered so that it can be used as well as possible for the Indonesian people. To deal with these problems, it is necessary to have a strategy that must be taken to strengthen supervision and reduce the threats and disturbances that will be caused in the Sunda Strait. Defense as one of the functions of government to achieve the ideals of the state by realizing state unity and integrity to achieve the nation's goals (Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 3 of 2002 concerning State Defense, 2002). The strengthening of defense in the Sunda Strait needs to be increased and can be used as a useful strategy to maintain national sovereignty.

Research methods

This research uses descriptive qualitative method, the qualitative research process does not have the factors that influence the data so that it aims to obtain real data in natural conditions. Descriptive research does not provide certain treatment, make manipulations or make changes to the variables under study, but rather provides an overview of the actual conditions (Bungin, 2007). The theory used in this research is the implementation theory according to Van Meter and Van Horn about the policy implementation approach model (Agostino, 2006), and the strategy theory from Lykke (Lykke Jr, 1989). This study uses the interview method conducted to informants, who are personnel who are appointed by officials of each agency and have competence in their fields, so that the aim of researchers to obtain information can be implemented properly.

Results and Discussion

The research carried out obtains data and discussion which will be described as follows:

Current marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait

The maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait has been implemented. Currently, securing the Sunda Strait is included in ALKI 1 Security Operations starting from the Malacca Strait to the Sunda Strait. Whereas the Sunda Strait Traffic Separation Scheme (TSS) was implemented on July 1, 2020 (Jurnal Maritim, 2020), TSS is a shipping lane separation scheme in a shipping lane, where the route has busy, narrow traffic and has many obstacles in navigation. . The determination of the TSS of the Sunda Strait in ensuring the safety of shipping vessels crossing the Sunda Strait is one of the implementations of the Indonesian Maritime Policy in accordance with Indonesia's vision to become a World Maritime Axis. With the implementation of TSS Sunda Strait, passing ships will feel more comfortable, because security is more guaranteed so that it will increase the volume and activity of shipping in the Sunda Strait. The increasing volume and activity of shipping in the Sunda Strait will also increase the threat that will arise in the Sunda Strait. The threats that will arise are not only military threats, but other threats that are increasingly complex and diverse. One of the very big threats is the circulation of drugs through the Sunda Strait. Research conducted using qualitative research that does not generalize research answers but by paying attention to the existing details, from all the answers put forward by informants in the research discussion have been adjusted to the theory of Van Meter Van Horn (1975). This theory explains that the implementation of policies to strengthen marine defense strategies through the determination of TSS in the Sunda Strait is influenced by the variables that the researchers have compiled. The results of the research based on field observations and interviews are:

1. Understanding of policy objectives

At the executive level, it must understand the general purpose of a policy objective. The objectives of the policy must be conveyed and understood by every implementer in the field. Based on the research results, policy implementers, in this case members of Lanal Banten, members of KAL Anyer, Ditpolair Polda Banten, Pengawak VTS Merak, understand the policy objectives, in this case the determination of the Sunda Strait TSS is one way to strengthen the marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait.

2. Resource

In implementing the policy of success in achieving by utilizing existing resources. Based on the results of the research, it was found that the existing facilities and infrastructure in the Sunda Strait related to the strengthening of marine defense strategies, are still very limited, the lack of patrol boat facilities, especially the presence of the KRI, the limited Integrated Maritime Surveillance System (IMSS) radar which is very much needed to assist carry out operations at sea, as well as human resources to support operations in the Sunda Strait.

3. Characteristics of Implementing Agencies

Based on the results of the study, it was found that the Indonesian Navy, Ministry of Transportation and Police agencies in carrying out their duties and responsibilities showed organizational characteristics that were compatible with the policy of enhancing marine defense strategies in the Sunda Strait. Each of the above organizations in carrying out their duties and authorities daily has carried out well. However, good coordination is needed in order to maintain marine defenses in the Sunda Strait.

4. Communication Between Implementing Agencies

From the results of field research with informants, it was found that communication and coordination between agencies in the Sunda Strait related to strengthening marine defense strategies had been well established. Not only formal communication but also informal communication between agencies. So that the operational implementation

of each agency can be carried out properly. However, there is a need for integration in order to synergize sea power and carry out joint operations around the Sunda Strait.

5. Disposition of the Implementers

The implementation of strengthening the marine defense strategy involves many agencies and personnel in the Sunda Strait region, not only military units but also existing civilian units. The attitude of the implementers who carry out policies related to marine defense strategies have carried out their duties properly. They carry out the regulations related to their respective agencies, this cannot be separated from the understanding they receive and also understand the objectives to be achieved. From the research that has been carried out, the researcher found that the attitude of the policy implementers has carried out their duties properly in accordance with their duties, functions and responsibilities. This is due to an understanding of the tasks they are given, as well as the training and education they receive before carrying out their duties. With this attitude, the policies that have been given can be implemented properly in their implementation.

6. The Influence of the Social, Economic and Political Environment

The success of a policy will be greatly influenced by the surrounding environment, whether the social, economic and political environment supports the policy. From the research that has been carried out, the researchers found that the influence of the social, economic and political environment in order to strengthen the marine defense strategy through the determination of the TSS of the Sunda Strait was well implemented. Not only the government in terms of making regulations regarding the TSS of the Sunda Strait but the people living in the Sunda Strait with their livelihoods as fishermen feel helped and support the TSS of the Sunda Strait.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors for the Strengthening of Marine Defense Strategies by Establishing TSS of the Sunda Strait

Based on the results of the research, it is found that the supporting factor in strengthening the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait is government support through regulations and other policies, especially the PMD Vision, because Indonesia's ability to manage the Sunda Strait is a sign that Indonesia is capable of managing and utilizing one of its marine resources. In addition, there is also great community support, in this case the users of the Sunda Strait. With the TSS Sunda Strait, it automatically increases the safety of Sunda Strait users. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factors for strengthening the marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait include the lack of part of the Sunda Strait user community, namely small fishermen who carry out fishing in restricted areas so that it can endanger shipping safety. There was no special operation undertaken by the Indonesian Navy in order to secure the TSS of the Sunda Strait, so that if there was a threat from the Sunda Strait it would take a lot of time to respond to this situation this happened because of the lack of KRI presence in the Sunda Strait. In addition, there is also a lack of facilities and infrastructure, in this case the sensors owned by the Banten lanal Meanwhile, the latter lacks human resources, in this case VTS crew and Lanal Banten personnel.

Discussion

Law No.34 of 2004 on the TNI states that the Indonesian Navy has the task of the TNI as the maritime element in the defense sector. The implementation of defense at sea is a task that is owned by the Navy. To realize this task, various efforts have been made, one of which is strengthening marine defense in the Sunda Strait. This strengthening cannot be separated from the threats that arise due to the increasing number of users of the Sunda Strait every year.

In the theory presented by Ken Booth in his book entitled "Navies and Foreign Policies," it is explained that, the roles that the navy have universally have three roles that are interrelated with one another, namely 1). Military role; 2). Diplomacy and Role; 3). The role of the police. In the military role, the navy has the duty to uphold the country's sovereignty at sea through elemental forces and bases, prepare for strength in the face of war, ward off

military threats that arise at sea through operations carried out, protect and guard borders at sea with neighboring countries, and protect security stability in the maritime area.

In the discussion of this research will answer the formulation of problems that have been determined by referring to the data obtained from the results of research on strengthening the marine defense strategy of Lanal Banten through the determination of TSS in the Sunda Strait. The current state of marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait is after the determination of the Sunda Strait Traffic Separation Scheme (TSS).

With the size of the maritime area and as a maritime country, Indonesia naturally can maximize its maritime potential for the advancement of the nation (Mustari & Barnas, 2018). With the determination of the TSS of the Sunda Strait, it is hoped that it will improve shipping safety and protection of the maritime environment so that it is well maintained. In addition, the determination of the TSS for the Sunda Strait gave a positive assessment to Indonesia and raised the name of the Indonesian nation in the international world in realizing the aspirations of the Indonesian nation to become a world maritime axis. Maritime security is no longer seen only as an effort to uphold security in a traditional context, but also to realize the maintenance of sea order, because there are many variables of objects of interest that exist in the sea, such as natural resources, means of transportation and environmental aspects (Keliat, 2009). The security operations carried out in ALKI - I, especially those carried out in the Sunda Strait, use the concept of maritime sovereignty in Indonesian waters, where the current operation uses the concept of the World Maritime Axis (Gunawan et al., 2018). From the results of research in the field that the strengthening of the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait is not optimal, it still needs to be improved, namely through several discussion variables as follows:

1. Understanding of Policy Objectives

The determination of TSS in the waters of the Sunda Strait aims to provide security in navigation navigation. This is in accordance with the government's objective in implementing the Nawa Mimpri program to make Indonesia a PMD. In Presidential Decree No. 16 of 2017 concerning Indonesian Maritime Policy. It is stated in article 1, point two, that PMD is a vision of Indonesia to become a maritime country that is sovereign, advanced, independent, strong, and capable of making a positive contribution to regional and world security and peace in accordance with national interests (Presidential Decree No. 16, 2017) For the implementation of strengthening the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait, the focus of this research is how the understanding of the defense security executing agencies in the Sunda Strait region can understand and understand and implement the objectives of the government regarding Indonesian maritime policy (KKI) on factors policy in point 2 about defense and security. In reality, in the field there are still a small number of fishermen who use the Sunda Strait as a place to find fish, do not yet understand the determination of the TSS of the Sunda Strait and the stipulation of prohibited areas for fishing. There is a need for socialization regarding the determination of TSS for the Sunda Strait and places that cannot be used for fishing in fishing communities.

2. Resource

In the theory of maritime strategy presented by Alfred Thyer Mahan in his book entitled *The Influence of Sea Power Upon History*, states "It is easy to say in a general way, that the use and control of the sea is and has been a great factor in. the history of the world; (Mahan., 1987). That the use and control of the sea is a very determining factor in world history. Maritime strategy is control of the sea, by ensuring the use of the sea for its own interests and closing all opportunities for opponents to use it. To protect and maintain this natural wealth, we need the right strategy to control the sea. This requires several resources, including:

a. Facilities and infrastructure

Researchers will discuss the facilities and infrastructure that can support the strengthening of marine defense strategies in the Sunda Strait. The facilities and infrastructure include the patrol boat and IMSS radar in the Sunda Strait. One of the facilities in the Sunda Strait is the Integrated Maritime Surveillance radar. System (IMSS). This radar serves to facilitate the supervision of ships passing through the Sunda

Strait (Dotulung, 2020). From the research, it is known that the IMSS radar in the Sunda Strait is currently experiencing damage.

Apart from the IMSS radar, one of the facilities it has is a patrol boat. Researchers will discuss the condition of the Lanal Banten facility, in this case the ship that is under the line of Lanal Banten. The need for patrol boats in order to create security in the Sunda Strait is an important factor. Apart from patrols carried out by the Indonesian Navy, other agencies also carry out patrols around the Sunda Strait, one of which is the Bakamla (Maritime Security Agency) and other agencies. KAL Anyer is currently carrying out the ALKI 1 security operation (Pam ALKI 1), securing the Sunda Strait is part of the ALKI1 security, Pam ALKI 1 stretches from the North Natuna Sea, Natuna Sea, Karimata Strait to the Sunda Strait. With the wide coverage of the Pam Alki 1 KAL Anyer operations, it was not continuously in the Sunda Strait so that there were very few elements of Indonesian Navy ships in the Sunda Strait. Supposedly, to strengthen the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait, two ships can be mobilized at any time to support operations in the Sunda Strait. This happened because there was no special operation to secure the Sunda Strait. It needs sufficient budget support in order to fulfill facilities and infrastructure. In fulfilling the budget, it is necessary to submit an RKA KL (Work Plan and Budget of Ministries and Institutions) submitted by the work units of each agency.

b. Human Resources

Lack of human resources in Lanal Banten must also be considered because the lack of personnel will hinder the success of the operation carried out. From the results of the interview, it was found that from the number of Lanal Banten's Personnel Composition List (DSP), which amounted to 250 people, only 168 people were filled or only 61%, the lowest level of fulfillment was Officer strata, which was only 43%. In carrying out operations, personnel who are directly involved in the operations unit (Sops) are required. Meanwhile, the fulfillment in the operation department was only fulfilled around 30%.

From the above discussion, it further adds to the confidence of researchers that control of the sea can be done by building a maritime security and defense system in the Sunda Strait through good facilities and infrastructure in the form of detection devices using advanced technology and the addition of elements of patrol boats that operate routinely so that they can oversee the entire Strait waters Sunda. Strengthening the defense system in the Sunda Strait can also take advantage of technological advances to modernize the integrated sensing system between Command, Control, Communication, Computers, Intelligence, Observation and Reconnaissance (K4IPP) (Ministry of Defense, 2015).

3. Characteristics of the Implementing Organization

Strengthening defense in the Sunda Strait is not only the task of the Indonesian Navy, in this case Lanal Banten, but also involves various maritime agencies around the Sunda Strait. The implementation of safeguards from the perspective of civilian power requires coordination and an agency that can carry out sea security guarding and safeguards supported by a clear legal basis. So that it will make a big contribution in terms of maintaining security and order and safety at sea.

From the results of research in the field with several sources, it can be concluded that the aforementioned agency in carrying out its daily tasks shows organizational characteristics that are compatible with the policy of improving marine defense strategies in the Sunda Strait. Each of the above organizations has the authority in accordance with their respective duties so that the implementation of the assigned tasks can be carried out properly. However, good coordination is needed in order to maintain maritime defenses in the Sunda Strait.

4. Communication Between Implementing Agencies

Communication is one thing that must be carried out in every operation. With good and effective communication, the goals to be achieved can be easily achieved. Geostrategic management in the Sunda Strait is a problem that cannot be solved sectorally by one agency alone, it needs the involvement of various agencies in an integrated manner. This requires good inter-agency communication.

Good communication through the establishment of an Online Crisis Center and the establishment of the Sunda Strait Operational Control Command Center (Puskodalops) will facilitate coordination and synergize existing Maritime forces.

5. Disposition of the Implementers

According to Van Meter and Van Horn, success in policy implementation really depends on the attitude of the implementers whether the implementing agency accepts or rejects the public policy.

The attitude of the implementers in accepting or rejecting a policy cannot be separated from understanding the objectives of a policy. The implementer's understanding of the stated policy objectives is a strong motivation for implementing the policy. In addition, the understanding that the implementers get depends also on the education they get.

6. The Influence of the Social, Economic and Political Environment

To achieve strong security and defense requires reliable control of the sea (Sea Power), Geoffrey Till in the book *Sea Power: A Guide For The Twenty-First Century*, says: Seapower is clearly a larger concept than landpower or airpower, neither of which encompasses the geo-economic dimensions of human activity to the extent that power does "(Geoffrey, 2009). Sea Power is a concept that is bigger than land or air power, both of which do not include geo-economic dimensions and human activities using the sea. The word sea power cannot be separated from the word Maritime power.

a. Social environment

In the creation of a strong maritime power, a basic component is needed, namely a maritime community that has an awareness of the importance of defense and security as well as supporting maritime resources. From this understanding, we can conclude that the realization of the strengthening of the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait requires the support of all maritime components in the Sunda Strait which is consistent, this is aimed at realizing maritime security stability which is the responsibility of all citizens.

b. Economic Factors

The determination of TSS for the Sunda Strait is one of the policies taken to improve the safety and smoothness of shipping in the Sunda Strait, another positive impact is the improvement of the economy of the surrounding community. The number of ships passing through the Sunda Strait opens opportunities for the surrounding community to increase their income by providing assistance facilities needed by users in the Sunda Strait. These include tug services, bunkering services, transit services including ship to ship transfers, ship spare parts supply services, crew replacement services, including insurance services.

c. Political Factors

Government support for the determination of the TSS for the Sunda Strait can be seen in the Decree of the Minister of Transportation No. KM 130 of 2020 concerning the establishment of the Route System in the Sunda Strait. through this regulation of the Minister of Transportation, it is clear that the TSS of the Sunda Strait has a legal basis. Other government support in determining the TSS for the Sunda Strait was also evident in the preparation of the TSS for the Sunda Strait, from upgrading the VTS of Merak to informing the international community through the digital world as well as delivery at international meetings regarding the implementation of the TSS for the Sunda Strait.

Lykke says that strategy consists of goals, means and means, we can formulate this concept with the equation:
Strategy = Goals (Ends) + Actions (Ways) + Instruments (Means)

This general concept can be used as a basis for formulating all kinds of military, political, economic and other strategies.

Through this theory, it is formulated that the strategy for strengthening in the Sunda Strait is to realize the "Ends" or the objectives of security, defense, law enforcement and ensuring safety for Sunda Strait users. By carrying out the mandate in accordance with applicable laws as a means or "means." And empowering the maritime component by integrating maritime forces and making use of existing resources. Meanwhile, "Ways" are used through efforts to increase public awareness to participate in improving security, law enforcement, and ensuring safety for marine users in the Sunda Strait through improved facilities and infrastructure, governance of authority, integrated operations, training, education, socialization to the community, fostering state defense to the people around the Sunda Strait. The following is the formulation of efforts to strengthen maritime defense strategies in the Sunda Strait through strategic analysis using the Ends, Means, Ways approach in the table below.

Table 1: Implementation of Theory's Strategy

End	Means	Ways
Implementers in the field understand and can implement defense and security policies	Guidelines for the implementation of duties as well as Inherent Supervision guidelines	The implementation of an inherent supervision system so that the executors carry out their duties properly. Providing provision in the education of each institution about understanding the duties and responsibilities.
Fulfillment of the needs for facilities and infrastructure in maintaining maritime security in the Sunda Strait with the latest technology	Submission through budget planning for improvement of maritime facilities and infrastructure in the Sunda Strait	Additional budget for agencies that need to improve maritime facilities and infrastructure
The establishment of the Sunda Strait control and operation Command Center	Through policies, cooperation between agencies, regulations	A control and operations command center was formed which involved all maritime agencies around the Sunda Strait
Fulfillment of Human Resources for manning maritime agencies	Submissions for additional maritime agency crew personnel through the personnel division of each agency	Increase the number of personnel in recruitment to meet human resource needs
The reduction of violations in the Sunda Strait region, the formation of public awareness of the importance of maritime security through awareness of defending the country and loving the country	State Defense Education	The local government collaborates with other agencies to promote awareness of state defense for the maritime community and promote socialization on the policy of determining TSS for the Sunda Strait.
Implementation of special operations to secure the Sunda Strait	Policies made by maritime agencies in the Sunda Strait	Strengthening security patrols with the deployment of ships around the Sunda Strait

Source: Rahmad, 2021

Conclusion

From the results of the research that has been carried out and the discussion that has been carried out regarding the strengthening of the marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait through the determination of the TSS of the Sunda Strait, the following conclusions are drawn:

- a. The current condition of the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait is not optimal, it is necessary to strengthen the title of the Navy elements operating in the Sunda Strait, currently there is only one

element, namely KAL Anyer who carries out the task of securing ALKI 1 so that the presence in the Sunda Strait is still lacking, it is necessary special operations degree for handling security in the Sunda Strait related to the busy shipping traffic crossing the Sunda Strait. For security factors related to international shipping, it is currently running smoothly, one of which is the establishment of the TSS of the Sunda Strait.

b. The supporting factor influencing the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait is the government's policy regarding Indonesia's Vision to become a World Maritime Axis. Apart from that, the support of the people in the Sunda Strait region has welcomed the policy of establishing the TSS of the Sunda Strait. Also maritime agencies in the Sunda Strait have good coordination, both formal and informal. Meanwhile, the inhibiting factor for strengthening the marine defense strategy in the Sunda Strait is that there are still fishing communities using the Sunda Strait who do not care about the regulations that have been set. Furthermore, there has been no special operation carried out by the Indonesian Navy to secure the Sunda Strait. Lack of facilities and infrastructure is also an obstacle to strengthening the maritime defense strategy in the Sunda Strait, the IMSS radar in the Sunda Strait is currently ready to be limited. Also lack of human resources for manning operations.

c. Efforts made to strengthen the marine defense strategy include the addition of elements of the Navy patrol through special operations to secure the Sunda Strait. Submission to repair the IMSS radar in the Sunda Strait so that the IMSS radar can function optimally again. The formation of the Sunda Strait Puskodalops, which consists of all maritime agencies in the Sunda Strait so that the handling of operations in the Sunda Strait can be well coordinated and synergized. Fulfillment of human resources must also be carried out by proposing additional personnel through applicable procedures. In addition, it is also necessary to conduct socialization and fostering awareness of State Defense for the communities around the Sunda Strait. It is also necessary to implement a policy of inherent supervision for personnel implementing policies in the field, so that the implementation of the assigned tasks can be carried out properly.

Recommendation

From the research that has been conducted by the author, the recommendations that will be given include:

a. Through the Coordinating Ministry for Maritime Affairs and Investment of the Republic of Indonesia, it is necessary to harmonize regulations in the maritime sector to make regulations that serve as guidelines for all maritime agencies in maritime security.

b. The Ministry of Transportation, in this case Sea Transportation, should form an Online Crisis Center and the Sunda Strait Operational Control Command Center (Puskodalops) to integrate maritime forces in the Sunda Strait in order to secure the Sunda Strait. Puskodalops Sunda Strait as a control center for operations carried out in the Sunda Strait starting from the field of security operations and handling problems around the Sunda Strait.

c. The Indonesian Navy, in this case the Chief of Staff of the Navy, to increase the budget for the maintenance of IMSS radars in the Sunda Strait.

d. Disminpersal to add personnel in Lanal Banten, or to provide additional education to improve the abilities of Lanal Banten members through LDD, courses and other education.

e. The Commander of Fleet 1 to make special operations in the context of securing the Sunda Strait by adding the title of elements (KRI assistance) that will be present in the waters of the Sunda Strait by taking into account the capabilities of the ship / KRI that will operate, the deployed elements can operate in the characteristic conditions of the Sunda Strait waters.

f. The Banten regional government to develop awareness of State Defense for Maritime community groups and instill the importance of love for the homeland through their respective fields so as to create resistance against emerging threats.

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